

Spectral, Magnetic and Thermal Studies of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) Chelates of 4-S-Benzyl-1-*p*-Cl-Phenyl-5-Phenyl-2, 4-Isodithiobiuret (BPPTB)

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Studies on the chelates of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) metal ions with the bidentate ligand 4-S-benzyl-1-*p*-Cl-phenyl-5-phenyl-2, 4-isodithiobiuret have been carried out. On the basis of the elemental analysis, thermal analysis and molar conductivity data, the chelates have been assigned as Co(BPPTB)₂, Ni(BPPTB)₂, Cu(BPPTB)₂·2H₂O and Pd(BPPTB)₂. Their electronic spectra, magnetic susceptibility as well as infrared spectra have been reported and discussed. Ni(II) chelate exhibits anomalous magnetic moment ($\mu = 1.06$ B.M.) at room temperature. This nature of Ni(II) chelate is discussed on the basis of the work reported earlier.

A literature survey showed that not much work has been done on the complex formation of dithiobiuretes¹⁻⁴. The complexes of 1, 5-disubstituted-2, 4-dithiobiuret with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Zn(II) were studied by Srivastava and Agarwal^{5,6}. Recently, Pignedoli *et al*⁷ have prepared the neutral and cationic complexes of Ni(II) with 1-phenyl-5-methyl-2, 4-dithiobiuret and suggested a tentative structure on the basis of electronic and infrared spectra. Kowel *et al*⁸ have explained the structure of the inner coordination sphere and bonding in Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes of 2, 4-dithiobiuret using infrared and Raman spectra. In this communication, we report the preparation and properties of complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Pd(II) with ligand. Tentative structure has been proposed for the chelates on the basis of spectral and magnetic susceptibility data and the results of chemical and thermal analysis and molar conductivity data.

Experimental

The chemicals used were all of AnalaR or chemically pure grade.

Preparation of the ligand :

4-S-benzyl-1-parachloro-phenyl-5-phenyl-2, 4-isodithiobiuret (BPPTB) was reported in literature in 1903 by Johnson and Elmer⁹. However, in the present studies it has been synthesised by simple method as modified by Mahajan *et al*¹⁰.

Preparation of the Metal Chelates :

Metal salts of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) were used in the form of their acetates in the preparation of their chelates, while Pd(II) was taken in the form of chloride. All the solutions of metal salts

except Pd(II) were prepared in distilled water while the solution of Pd(II) chloride was prepared in dilute HCl adjusting its pH between 0.5-1.0. Ligand solution was prepared in methanol.

An aqueous solution of metal salts was gradually added with vigorous stirring to the methanolic solution of reagent in 1 : 2 (M : L) molar ratio. The solution was diluted with distilled water till coloured chelates separated out. It was digested on water bath for about 15 minutes, cooled, filtered and washed with hot water and methanol several times. It was dried in an desiccator over calcium chloride and recrystallised from solvent ether. The results of analysis of the chelates are given in Table 1.

Physical Measurements :

Magnetic measurements (Tables 1 and 2), visible and ultra violet spectra (Tables 3 and 4), reflectance spectra (Table 3), infrared spectra (Table 5) and conductance measurements for all the chelates were studied as reported earlier¹¹. T.G.A. studies were performed in the Chemistry Department of I.I.T., Bombay¹². The thermoanalytical data of the chelates in the present study is detailed in Table 6.

Results and Discussion

Magnetic Measurements :

The magnetic moment of Co(II) chelate of BPPTB is 4.65 B.M. at room temperature. Carlin¹³ observed a magnetic moment value of 4.73 B.M. for Co(II) complex of ethylene thiourea at room temperature and it is temperature independent, with the value of $\Theta = -11^\circ\text{K}$ and suggested tetrahedral geometry to the Co(II) complex. In the present case magnetic moment value are

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, COLOUR, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE IN NITROBENZENE AND μ_{eff} AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Chelate	M% Found (Reqd)	C% Found (Reqd)	H% Found (Reqd)	N% Found (Reqd)	S% Found (Reqd)	Colour	M*	μ_{eff} B.M. (294.5°K)
Co(BPPTB) ₂	6.72 (6.69)	58.20 (57.27)	4.04 (3.86)	9.50 (9.54)	14.50 (14.54)	Green	5.00	4.65
Ni(BPPTB) ₂	6.75 (6.67)	57.30 (57.29)	3.89 (3.86)	9.30 (9.54)	14.20 (14.55)	Blue	3.90	1.06
Cu(BPPTB) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	6.85 (6.90)	52.10 (54.74)	3.97 (4.12)	9.12 (9.20)	13.65 (13.90)	Light green	10.95	1.99
Pd(BPPTB) ₂	11.35 (11.47)	54.00 (54.34)	3.70 (3.66)	9.15 (9.05)	13.90 (13.84)	Orange	9.50	Dia

M* = Molar Conductance $M(\text{ohm}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^2\cdot\text{mol}^{-1})$ in $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of nitrobenzene at 25°.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC DATA AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temperature (°K)	Co(II)-BPPTB			Temperature (°K)	Cu(II)-BPPTB		
	Diamagnetic correction : -189 × 10 ⁻⁶ erg G ⁻² mole ⁻¹		μ_{eff} (B.M.)		Diamagnetic correction : -215 × 10 ⁻⁶ erg G ⁻² mole ⁻¹		μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	$\chi \text{ Co} \times 10^6$ (erg G ⁻² mole ⁻¹)	$\chi \text{ Co}^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$ (G ² mole erg ⁻¹)		$\chi \text{ Cu} \times 10^6$ (erg G ⁻² mole ⁻¹)	$\chi \text{ Cu}^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$ (G ² mole erg ⁻¹)		
294.5	9,205	1.086	4.65	294.5	1,6949	5.900	1.99
273.0	9,890	1.011	4.65	260.5	1,8869	5.300	1.98
250.0	10,820	0.925	4.65	245.0	1,9973	5.006	1.97
210.5	12,882	0.776	4.66	210.0	2,2769	4.392	1.95
173.0	15,607	0.640	4.65	150.0	3,2269	3.098	1.96
104.0	25,970	0.389	4.65	102.0	4,5726	2.198	1.93

⊖ = -9°K

⊖ = 10°K

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS AND THEIR ASSIGNMENTS

Complex	Reflectance spectra		Absorption spectra (Chloroform)		Assignment
	λ_{max} nm	λ_{max} kK	λ_{max} nm	λ_{max} kK	
Co(II)-BPPTB	690	14.50	700(sh)	14.28	⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)
	630	15.87	600	16.66	
	520	19.23	520	19.23	
Ni(II)-BPPTB	670	14.92	620	16.12	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g}
	640	15.62			
	580	17.41	560	17.85	
Cu(II)-BPPTB	870	11.49			² B _{1g} → ² A _{1g}
	700	14.29	720	13.88	
	620	16.23	640	15.62	
Pd(II)-BPPTB			550	18.18	² B _{1g} → ² E _g
			510	19.61	
	410	24.30			
			350	38.57	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ E _{1g}
			280	35.71	

temperature independent, (Table 2 and ⊖ = -9°K.) This indicates tetrahedral character of Co(II) chelate of BPPTB. The magnetic moment of Ni(II) chelate is found to be 1.06 B.M. which is unusual and lower than spin only value of two unpaired electrons. Holt *et al*¹⁴ and others¹⁵⁻¹⁷ suggested that partial paramagnetic moment of Ni(II) complex may be attributed to the square planar tetrahedral equilibrium. Therefore, a square planar geometry can be suggested for Ni(II) chelate in the present case. Magnetic moment value of Cu(II) chelate is nearly same over a temperature range 100-294.5°K which obey the Curie-Weiss law and have a ⊖ = 10°K indicating neither inter nor intramolecular Cu-Cu interaction¹⁸. Chelate of Pd(II) in the present study is diamagnetic, hence square planar geometry is suggested.

Electronic Spectra :

TABLE 4—ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF THE LIGAND AND ITS METAL CHELATE IN UV REGION

Species	λ_{max} nm	λ_{max} nm	log ϵ	Assignments
BPPTB	310	32.26	3.85	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
Co(BPPTB) ₂	300	33.33	4.63	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
	245	40.82	4.52	$P_y \pi \rightarrow \pi^*, \pi \rightarrow d$
Ni(BPPTB) ₂	295	33.90	4.62	$\pi_s \rightarrow \pi_s^*$
	245	40.82	4.51	$P_y \pi \rightarrow \pi^*, \pi \rightarrow d$
Cu(BPPTB)	270	37.04	4.53	$\pi_s \rightarrow \pi_s^*$
	245	40.82	4.60	$P_y \pi \rightarrow \pi^*, \pi \rightarrow d$

The diffuse reflectance spectra and absorption spectra in chloroform of Co(II)-BPPTB chelate exhibit intense multiple bands in the region 14 kK-19.25 kK. On the basis of experimental results and observation made by earlier workers^{19,20}, a tetrahedral geometry can be suggested for Co(II)-BPPTB chelate and multiple bands in the electronic spectra at 14 kK-19.25 kK can be accounted for ⁴A_{2g} → ⁴T_{1g}(P) transitions. The reflectance and absorption spectra of Ni(II)-BPPTB chelate show multiple bands

TABLE 5—INFRARED AND SPECTRAL DATA OF BPPTB AND METAL COMPLEXES

BPPTB	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Pd(II)	Assignments
3560 _{m,sp}	—	—	—	—	N-H-ph stretching
3200 _{sp}	3260 _{sp}	3380 _{sp}	3200 _b	3100 _b	N-H stretching
1560 _{sp}	1590 _{sp}	1590 _{sp}	1590 _{b,m}	1600 _{m,sp}	C-N stretching
1400 _b	1390 _{sp}	1390 _{sp}	1400 _{sp}	1400 _{m,sp}	S-CH ₂ stretching
1210 _{sp}	1200 _{sp}	1200 _{sp}	1200 _{sp}	1215 _{m,sp}	S-CH ₂ -ph
695 _{sp}	690 _{sp}	690 _{sp}	690 _{sp}	690 _{sp}	C=S stretching
—	—	—	3400 _b	—	Lattice water
—	540 _m	520 _{m,w}	530 _{m,w}	530 _w	M-N
—	390-420 _w	380-400 _m	410-420 _w	390-420 _{m,w}	M-S

m=medium ; sp=sharp , w=weak ; b=broad.

TABLE 6—THERMOANALYTICAL DATA OF METAL COMPLEXES OF BPPTB

Temperature °C	%weight loss		Probable composition
	Found	Calculated	
560	Co(BPPTB) ₂		Co ₂ O ₄
	87.00	90.88	
580	Ni(BPPTB) ₂		NiO
	89.00	91.51	
190	Cu(BPPTB) ₂ .2H ₂ O		Cu(BPPTB) ₂
	4.50	3.90	
540	Pd(BPPTB) ₂		CuO
	89.00	91.36	
640	87.50	86.81	PdO

around 15 kK-18 kK. The bands at 14.92 kK and 17.41 kK may be assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{2g}$ transitions respectively²¹. Drago²² and Holm²³ have suggested tetragonal or square planar geometry for Ni(II) complexes on the basis of similar spectral transition. The diffuse reflectance spectra of Cu(II)-BPPTB chelate show a band in 11 kK-20 kK region and absorption spectra show bands with shoulder in the range 12 kK-24 kK. Hatway *et al*^{24,25} have also observed two main bands at about 14 kK-15.60 kK and 9.20 kK-10.80 kK in the electronic spectra of Cu(II) complexes and suggested distorted octahedral geometry for Cu(II) complexes. The observed electronic spectra of Pd(II) chelate suggest square planar geometry for this chelate^{26,27}.

Electronic spectra in the UV region of the metal chelates and ligand show two or more bands in range of 32-37 kK (Table 4). Transitions of the band and their assignments are given in Table 4. The trends of the bands are in good agreement with the observations made by earlier workers²⁸⁻³¹.

Infrared Spectra :

On examination of ir spectra of ligand (BPPTB) a strong band has been observed at 3050-3150 cm^{-1} . This band is due to -NH stretching vibration^{32,33,34}. The weakening of the -NH stretching frequency is observed on the chelate formation with a shift to slight higher frequency, which may probably be caused by the drainage of the electrons from the nitrogen to metal atom upon chelation³⁵. The ir spectra of ligand show one sharp band at

1400 cm^{-1} and strong band at 1210 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the -S-CH₂ and -C-S-CH₂-ph respectively³⁴. These have been found at same position in the metal chelates with medium or nearly same intensity. This observation may suggest that -S-CH₂-ph is free in the chelate and indicative of not taking part in the chelate formation. Another strong band at 1550 cm^{-1} ³⁴ in ligand may be assigned to C-N stretching frequency, which appears at 1580-1600 cm^{-1} in the metal chelates. A fairly strong band at 1500 cm^{-1} in the ligand and metal chelates may be due to mixed vibration of C=S stretching, -C-N stretching and -NH bonding modes^{36,37}. A fairly sharp band at 720-690 cm^{-1} in the ligand has been found at nearly the same position in metal chelates. This indicates major contribution of C=S stretching and C-N bonding vibration^{36,38}. An increase of the C-N stretching frequency and a decrease of the same C=S frequencies for the metal chelates with respect to ligand indicate that ligand is coordinated to the metal through S atom^{21,39}. In the region 500-550 cm^{-1} , the metal chelates show a new absorption peak which is not observed in the spectra of ligand. Various workers⁴⁰⁻⁴⁴ have assigned the M-N stretching modes in the Co, Ni, Cu and Pd chelates to the bands in the region 500-600 cm^{-1} . Metal-sulphur stretching frequencies usually lie within the range 480-210 cm^{-1} ^{21,40,45-47}.

Thermogravimetric Analysis :

Chelates of Co(II) and Ni(II) : The mass loss curves of these chelates are shown as curve A and B in Fig. 1. Examination of TG curve indicates that both the chelates do not contain water of hydration. Co(II) chelate is stable upto 110° and after the decomposition takes place as shown by rapid mass loss curve. Ni(II) chelate is found to be stable upto 200° and further rapid mass loss is observed due to oxidation reduction reactions.

Chelate of Cu(II) : According to the mass loss curve (Fig. 1, Curve C) Cu(BPPTB)₂.2H₂O loses its water of hydration in one step between 100 and 190° (4.50% found, 3.90% ther.) followed by rapid mass loss.

Fig. 1. TGA Curves

Chelate of Pu(II): This chelate contain no water of hydration (Fig. 1, Curve D) and is found to be stable upto 150°, after that continuous mass loss is observed.

In all the chelates of BPPTB except Pd(BPPTB)₂ chelate it is observed that there is small increase in the weight of residue after 500° [for Co(BPPTB)₂—weight of the residue increases beyond 595°, for Ni(BPPTB)₂—weight of the residue increases beyond 600° while for Cu(BPPTB)₂.2H₂O—weight of the residue increases beyond 540°]. Such type of results have been obtained by Sceney *et al*^{4,5,6} and suggested that the increase in weight is due to the oxidation of Cu₂S to CuO and CuSO₄.

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